

The Effect of Social Media on Consumers' Westernization, Lifestyle Dimensions, and Materialism in the Arabian Gulf: The Case of Kuwait

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Abstract

This study examined the influence of social media usage on lifestyle, westernization, and materialism among Kuwaiti consumers. Findings showed that Kuwaiti respondents' social media usage was moderate. Data analysis revealed a significant impact of social media engagement on several aspects of consumer lifestyle, including increased online impulsive buying and social comparisons, as well as a decline in body image satisfaction. Results also indicated that social media usage had a positive impact on materialism and westernization among Kuwaiti respondents.

Keywords: Social Media Involvement, Materialism, Westernization, Kuwaiti Consumers, GCC Lifestyle, Online Impulsive Buying, Social Comparisons, Body Image Satisfaction.

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1. Introduction

A digital cultural revolution is taking place in the Gulf as more young people use social media to express themselves creatively and forge unique identities (Almahmoud, 2021). More than half of Gulf consumers are under 25, making them part of one of the world's youngest markets. Despite Gulf consumers earning significantly more than their Arab counterparts, the data from the IMF's World Economic Outlook shows that the majority of them remain middle class. On a global scale, it is estimated that 33% of worldwide social media purchasing is expected to come from millennials, with 29% expected from Gen Z, and 28% from Gen X. Furthermore, 41% of Gen Z and Millennials reported making an impulse purchase online every 2-3 weeks as a result of social media exposure. It is estimated that there are over 82 million Arab social media users. More specifically, it has been noted that consumers in the Arabian Gulf use social media extensively, which has transformed how they connect, communicate, and shop, especially among younger generations. Therefore, social media for the Gulf consumer is becoming not just an interaction tool; it is a lifestyle.

2. Social media engagement

The term "social media engagement" describes how users interact with content on social media sites, including likes, comments, shares, and other behaviours that show audience participation. It shows the degree of interest and engagement that users have with the content. Social media enables real-time interaction between brands and customers, allowing businesses to address concerns, answer questions, and gather feedback (Jeswani, 2023). Increased customer engagement can lead to higher brand awareness, website traffic, and ultimately, sales for companies on social media (Amirrudin et al., 2024).

Research shows that 95.9% of Kuwait's population is actively engaged in social media; therefore, these platforms dominate daily life, shaping opinions, trends, values, and even purchasing decisions (Almutawaa & AlWazzan, 2024). Social media has fueled a trend of overbuying and impulse purchases in the Arabian Gulf, with consumers compulsively purchasing items they may not necessarily need (Azazz & Elshaer, 2022). Research also indicates that around 49% of consumers decide what to buy with influencer recommendations on social media, and that around 80% of consumers worldwide have purchased something after seeing it recommended by an influencer (Wang et al., 2024). As stated by Dalimunthe et al. In 2023, 76% of consumers bought a product after seeing it in a brand's social media post: 11% did so right away, 44% did so online, and 21% did so in a physical store. Furthermore, 65% of customers reported that a post's link directed them to a product they were not initially interested in buying.

According to Pauliene & Sedneva's (2019) research, 78% of consumers are "severely" impacted by consumer trends and the content they are exposed to on social media, including advertisements and the accounts of friends or groups. 59% of social media users make "unplanned" purchases based on what they see on social media, according to another study (Yang et al., 2024). For businesses, "presentation" on social media is thus far more crucial than it is in other forms of advertising. Additionally, it is estimated that approximately 61.5% of social media users consult friends or specialized pages to assess the product they wish to purchase, viewing them as a "reference" and following the recommendations of specific pages or celebrities (Zafar et al., 2021). Moreover, the COVID pandemic hastened social media adoption (Alhaimer, 2021), which was crucial in influencing consumers' opinions, social interaction patterns, and aspects of their lifestyles (Delogu et al., 2025), as well as those of the public.

3. Effect of social media on lifestyle dimensions

Activities, Interests, and Opinions (AIO) is a widely used approach to understanding lifestyle, focusing on what consumers do, what they care about, and their beliefs (Fernández et al., 2007; Dai & Zhang, 2021; Zhao & Lyu, 2022; Špindler et al., 2025). Activities reflect how consumers spend their time and money, including work, hobbies, social events, and shopping habits. Interests reflect what consumers find engaging and important, such as family, career, community, or specific products and brands. Opinions reflect consumers' views of themselves, social issues, politics, and other topics, shaping their attitudes and purchasing decisions. For this study, three variables will reflect the (AIO) of consumer lifestyle dimensions. More specifically, consumers' impulsive buying (to reflect activities), attention to social comparison (to reflect interests), and satisfaction with body image (to reflect opinions).

3.1 Impulsive buying and social media

Impulsive buying is defined as a consumer's unplanned buying behaviour (Adelaar et al., 2003) or any purchase made without advanced planning beforehand (Crawford & Melewar, 2003). Consumers buy impulsively when they experience a sudden, often powerful, and persistent urge to purchase a product immediately (Zhou & Wong, 2004). Therefore, impulsive buying is driven by high emotional activation, low cognitive control, and largely reactive consumer behaviour. Social media significantly influences impulsive buying, with many users making unplanned purchases after seeing products or promotions online (Yang et al., 2024). This influence is amplified by the interactive nature of social platforms and the prevalence of influencer marketing (Liu et al., 2025). For social media users, seeing friends or groups purchase or discuss certain items can also create a strong desire to acquire them. Research indicates that a substantial portion of social media users have made impulse purchases, and these can lead to either immediate gratification or later regret (Nuseir, 2020).

As for the Arabian Gulf, a study by Singh et al. (2024) among Saudi respondents also confirmed a significant positive effect of social media use on impulsive buying among Saudi consumers. Al-Abdallah et al. (2021) conducted a comprehensive GCC study of 1257 respondents, in which social media engagement was found to significantly influence the decision to buy luxury cars, with the most significant impact observed in the first two stages of the process (need recognition and information search). Another study indicated that Saudi women consumers are more impulsive in making unplanned purchase decisions than men, which was attributed to the effect of influencers on social media (Hashem, 2021). Building on the findings of the previous literature, the current study adopts the following hypothesis:

H1: Social media engagement has a significant positive effect on consumers' impulsive buying online.

3.2 Social comparison and social media

Social comparison is the act of evaluating oneself against others, often to assess one's abilities, opinions, or social standing (Suls & Wheeler, 2012). Social media provides a continuous stream of information about others, making it easier to engage in social comparison, often unconsciously (Burke et al., 2020). Studies show that social media use, particularly when coupled with social comparison, can contribute to adverse psychological outcomes, such as low self-esteem and disordered eating habits (Bonfanti et al., 2025). People tend to present their best selves online, often sharing highlights and carefully crafted images, which can create a skewed perception of reality. This curated content can make other consumers feel like they do not measure up to their peers (Strimbu & O'Connell, 2019; Zheng et al., 2020).

With the use of "likes" and "comments" on social media, allowing for real-time feedback, there is pressure to compete with online peers. Even online friends can serve as a reference point for consumers to compare their own preferences and behaviours with those of their friends through social comparison on social media (Lubbers et al.,

2009; Liu et al., 2016). This carefully chosen, often idealized, content shared on social media platforms can trigger upward social comparisons, in which individuals compare themselves to others who are perceived as superior (Kawamoto, 2021). This effect is amplified by constant exposure to filtered, often unrealistic portrayals of others' lives (Ruan et al., 2023). However, it is important to note that the impact of social media on social comparison varies. Some studies have shown that individuals with a higher tendency to compare themselves to others are more vulnerable to the adverse effects of social media (De Vries & Kühne, 2015; Samra, 2022; Tian, 2025).

Few studies have looked at how social media affects consumers' social comparison in the Arabian Gulf. For instance, Al-Sada (2022) found that, among adult social media users in Qatar, social media positively encourages social comparison. Al Azri et al. (2025) came to a similar conclusion in Oman. They examined a sample of 2,285 Omani participants (mean age 22.6 years; 76.5 percent female) and discovered a significant correlation between increased anxiety and decreased well-being and Instagram engagement. The findings also showed that the adverse effects of anxiety and well-being were more severe for those who had greater propensities for social comparison. Anxiety levels were higher among female participants, and age analysis indicated that vulnerability decreased after the age of thirty. According to Al Azri et al. (2025), Omani users' psychological distress is linked to social media content combined with upward social comparison. Building on the previously illustrated literature, the current study tests the following hypothesis to extend the previously mentioned findings.

H2: Social media engagement significantly increases consumers' attention to online social comparison.

3.3 Satisfaction with body image and social media

A person's perception of their body's size, shape, and general appearance, as well as its function, is referred to as body image satisfaction (Goswami et al. 2012). According to Lee et al. (2025), satisfaction with body image is a subjective perception influenced by a range of variables, including cultural and media messages and individual experiences. According to Yang et al. (2025), positive body image is demonstrated through showing respect, acceptance, and appreciation for one's body. In contrast, negative self-perception and body image are linked to discontent according to Barnett et al. (2020). Furthermore, body image satisfaction encompasses not only how a person sees their body but also their emotional and cognitive responses to that perception (Rodgers et al., 2023).

Platforms like Instagram, YouTube, and TikTok showcase trends and ideals, influencing beauty standards and potentially leading to body image issues and dissatisfaction. Numerous studies (Holland & Tiggemann, 2016; Qi, et al. 2017; Jarman, et al. 2021; Arjona, et al. 2024; Merino, et al. 2024; Yadav, 2025; Vendemia, 2025) have demonstrated that social media exposure causes physical discontent and unhealthy eating habits by promoting the ideal of thinness that people strive for. Research specifically indicates that young people, in particular, may develop a negative body image as a result of exposure to unrealistic body ideals promoted on social media (Bonfanti et al., 2025; Czubaj et al., 2025).

Research literature within the GCC has also reached similar conclusions. For instance, AlKindi et al. (2021) found a significant negative psychological impact of social media on perceived body image standards and a significant relationship between social media and harmful practices aimed at achieving the ideal body image among surveyed UAE respondents. The study examined the relationship between social media and body standards, and the nature of social media's impact on youth's body standards in Dubai. The study involved 150 respondents from Dubai.

Buali et al. (2024) examined the connection between social media use and body dysmorphic disorder, a mental illness in which a person obsesses over physical imperfections that are frequently invisible to others. The study drew a convenience sample of 444 respondents from Bahrain. The results confirmed that increased social media usage among respondents was associated with body dysmorphic disorder, Buali et al. (2024) also verified that body dysmorphic disorder was linked to comparing one's body image to that of others on social media and making assumptions about other people based on their appearance. In conclusion, Buali et al. (2024) found a strong correlation between Bahraini respondents' use of social media for songs, fashion, music, and celebrities and body dysmorphic disorder.

The analysis by Al Riyami et al. (2024) of 482 undergraduate Omani students (100 males and 382 females) also supported the link between body image dissatisfaction and social media use, suggesting that frequent social media use is associated with greater body image dissatisfaction. Riyami Al et al. (2024) also verified that a greater percentage of Omani respondents who had a negative body image spent six to ten hours a day on social media. The conclusion that increased social media usage is linked to higher levels of body image dissatisfaction was reached because students with low social media usage reported the lowest levels of body image dissatisfaction. Additionally, Al Riyami et al. (2024) found a significant correlation between high levels of body image dissatisfaction among Omani respondents and passive social media use, defined as the passive consumption of content without active interaction. In line with the previous research findings, the current study adopts the

following hypothesis:

H3: Social media engagement has a significant adverse effect on consumers' satisfaction with her/his own body image.

4. Social media and consumer materialism

The degree to which a person views possessions and their acquisition as a source of fulfilment and happiness is known as consumer materialism (Flouri, 1999). It is a personal value system where material goods are seen as important for personal well-being and social status. While some level of materialism is normal, excessive consumer materialism can be associated with adverse outcomes, such as lower life satisfaction, financial difficulties, and psychological distress (Semmler & Bobby, 2013). Since materialism influences individual consumption and, consequently, the economy, it has significant social ramifications. However, excessive buying and consumption can contribute to a culture of materialism and waste, with items purchased and overconsumed without careful consideration (Lekavičienė et al., 2022).

Social media has a significant impact on consumer materialism, often increasing materialistic values and influencing purchase behaviour (Jameel et al., 2024). Exposure to ideal online content, particularly influencer marketing, can trigger the desire to acquire similar possessions, leading to increased consumption of conspicuous products (Dávila & Casabayó, 2025). This effect is further amplified by the ease of online shopping and the constant exposure to advertising on social media platforms (Pellegrino & Shannon, 2022). Research suggests that social media engagement, even passive consumption (browsing without active engagement), can be positively correlated with materialistic values (Thi & Yoonjae, 2024).

In relation to the Arabian Gulf, social media is significantly shaping consumer materialism, particularly among youth, by influencing attitudes towards luxury goods and purchasing behaviours (Alsalloum & Gainous, 2025). This influence creates a desire to acquire status symbols to project a particular image on social media (Hurley, 2019). In a comparative study of Arab and American consumers by Kamal et al. (2013), it was found that materialism is a consequence of social media use for both samples. Furthermore, compared to American users, Arab social media users demonstrated higher levels of materialism and social media usage.

Jameel et al. (2024), who carried out a later study in Saudi Arabia, also confirmed that materialism mediated the relationship between social media usage and television advertisements, and that social media use is positively correlated with compulsive shopping behaviour among Saudi students. Similar findings were reported earlier by Arthur et al. (2017), who found that due to increased peer competition on social media, UAE citizens reported substantially higher levels of materialism than non-natives. Considering the significant findings in previous literature, the current research aims to adopt the following hypothesis:

H4: Social media engagement has a significant positive effect on consumers' materialism.

5. Consumer westernization and social media

Consumer Westernization refers to the adoption of Western consumer culture, including preferences, behaviours, and purchasing patterns, by individuals in non-Western societies. This phenomenon is often driven by factors such as globalization and exposure to Western media and culture (Kavisha et al., 2024). It can manifest in various ways, such as increased demand for Western brands, changes in food habits, and shifts in lifestyle choices (Sajib et al., 2016). Social media is often seen as Western media in non-Western cultures, shaping global narratives that influence people's views on modernity and tradition (Khan et al., 2025). This perspective holds that social media makes it easier for Western cultural trends to spread quickly, weakening regional customs, languages, and identities (Balogun & Aruoture, 2024).

Such view was confirmed by Das & Jebarajakirthy (2020) who surveyed 692 high-income Indian Gen-Y consumers to examine how their inclination toward Western cultural influence affects their intention to purchase Western luxury fashion. Results indicated that respondents' exposure to Western media, social interactions with Western culture, the exposure to marketing efforts by Western multinational companies, and a willingness to imitate Western culture all elevate the likelihood of purchasing Western luxury fashion. The findings also confirmed the positive effect of materialism, which significantly enhances these effects among the Indian respondents.

As for the GCC region, social media has significantly impacted the Arabian Gulf consumer, leading to both westernization and social change, particularly among younger generations (Rahman & Al-Azm, 2023). This impact

is evident in increased consumerism, shifts in social norms, and new forms of communication and empowerment (Pripoae-Șerbănescu & Mațoi, 2023). One of the most evident signs of Western social media's influence on Arabian Gulf consumers is that English remains the dominant language on their social media platforms. For instance, on Twitter, 88% of users in the UAE tweet in English, followed by 87% in Qatar, 81% in Bahrain, 78% in Kuwait, and 60% in both Oman and Saudi Arabia. This western influence was also highlighted by Pripoae-Șerbănescu & Mațoi (2023), who observed that social media could shape Gulf Generation Z by encouraging them to imitate specific Western behavioural patterns.

Social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Snapchat, and Instagram expose Gulf consumers to Western lifestyles, fashion, and products. This exposure, combined with rising disposable incomes and state-led initiatives, has fuelled a surge in demand for Western products and services, contributing to a more Westernized consumer-driven market (Assad, 2006). The younger Generation Z, who adapt, respond, and contribute their own ideas through social media, are highly open and accepting of westernization trends as active consumers and creators within the GCC's social media landscape (Brzuszkiewicz, 2025). However, such exposure to Western cultural norms through social media can lead to a perceived decline in traditional values, particularly among youth, who may find themselves caught between their cultural upbringing and the influences they encounter online. Data from the Arab Youth Survey (Asda'a BCW, 2022) across 17 Arab countries indicates that Arab youth view the Arabic language as less important than their parents do, yet they are concerned about the erosion of traditional values and culture. Additionally, they report difficulty in disconnecting from social media, which remains a daily source of information (Asda'a BCW, 2022). Considering the previously mentioned literature, the current study adopts the following hypothesis:

H5: Social media engagement has a significant positive effect on consumers' westernization.

6. Research methodology

The research follows a quantitative approach, surveying a convenience sample of consumers in Kuwait. An online questionnaire directed towards Kuwaiti consumers was administered in Arabic. Back-translation procedures were used as a quality assurance measure to verify the accuracy of the scales translated for cross-cultural research (Klotz et al., 2023). During the three-month sampling period, 514 usable responses were collected. All research variables used a Likert scale format. The current study used the social media engagement scale developed by Ferreira et al. (2020), the impulsive buying scale from Badgaiyan et al. (2016), and the consumer social comparison scale from Petrescu et al. (2025). The body image satisfaction scale was adopted from Bardi et al. (2021), and the consumer materialism scale was developed by Segev et al. (2015). The consumer westernization scale was also adopted from Sajib et al. (2016). Parametric statistics were used to analyse the collected data through the SPSS software.

7. Data Analysis

Cronbach's Alpha test revealed high scale reliability for all research variables, as shown in Table 1.

Table 3 Cronbach Alpha Values for Study Variables

Scale Name	Cronbach Alpha Value
Social media engagement	0.96
Impulsive buying	0.94
Social comparison	0.90
Satisfaction with body image	0.85
Materialism	0.95
Westernization	0.98

Descriptive statistics showed that the level of social media involvement amongst Kuwaiti consumers is concentrated around a moderate value, where the majority of respondents (51%) demonstrated a moderate level of involvement, whereas 24 21% of respondents reported a weak level of involvement, and strong level of involvement, respectively, as shown in Table 2.

Table 4 Social Media Engagement Level

Social Media Engagement	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Very Weak	6	1.2	1.2	1.2
Weak	123	23.9	23.9	25.1
Moderate	262	51.0	51.0	76.1
Strong	109	21.2	21.2	97.3
Very Strong	14	2.7	2.7	100.0
Total	514	100.0	100.0	

Regression analysis revealed a statistically significant positive effect of social media engagement on consumers' online impulsive buying, as shown in Table 3.

Table 5 Regression Analysis of H1

R Square 0.600	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.679	.085		7.941	.000
Social Media Engagement	.775	.028	.774	27.686	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Impulsive Buying

The B Unstandardized Coefficient shows a strong effect of social media engagement on consumers' impulsive buying, with a 1-point increase in social media engagement predicting a 0.775-point increase in impulsive buying online (holding all other variables constant). Furthermore, the R-square test of model fit indicated that 60% of the variance in consumers' impulsive buying can be explained by social media engagement. Therefore, H1 is accepted.

Regression analysis also revealed a statistically significant positive effect of social media engagement on consumers' attention to online social comparison, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Regression Analysis of H2

R Square 0.593	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.779	.084		9.288	.000
Social Media Engagement	.751	.027	.770	27.320	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Attention to Social Comparison

The B Unstandardized Coefficient shows a strong effect of social media engagement on consumers' attention to social comparison, where every increase of 1 point in social media engagement is predicted to increase consumers' attention to social comparison online by 0.751 points (holding all other variables constant). Furthermore, the R-square test of model fit indicated that 59% of the variance in consumers' attention to social comparison can be explained by social media engagement. Therefore, H2 is accepted.

Regarding the third hypothesis, regression analysis revealed a statistically significant adverse effect of social media engagement on consumers' satisfaction with their own body image, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5 Regression Analysis of H3

R Square 0.798	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	5.502	.057		96.037	.000
Social Media Engagement	-.845	.019	-.893	-45.018	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction with Body Image

The B Unstandardized Coefficient shows a substantial adverse effect of social media engagement on consumers' impulsive buying. For every 1-point increase in social media engagement, consumers' satisfaction with their body image is predicted to decrease by 0.845 points (holding all other variables constant). Furthermore, the R-square test of model fit indicated that approximately 80% of the variance in consumers' dissatisfaction with their body image can be explained and predicted by social media engagement. Therefore, H3 is accepted.

Furthermore, regression analysis revealed a statistically significant positive effect of social media engagement on consumers' materialism (see Table 6).

Table 6 Regression Analysis of H4

R Square 0.533	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.841	.095		8.830	.000
Social Media Engagement	.755	.031	.730	24.188	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Materialism

The B Unstandardized Coefficient shows a strong effect of social media engagement on consumers' materialism. For every 1-point increase in social media engagement, consumers' materialism is predicted to increase by 0.755 points (holding all other variables constant). Furthermore, the R-square test of model fit indicated that 53% of the variance in consumers' materialism can be explained by social media engagement. Therefore, H4 is accepted.

As for the fifth hypothesis, regression analysis also revealed a statistically significant positive effect of social media engagement on consumers' westernization, as shown in Table 7.

Table 7 Regression Analysis of H5

R Square 0.647	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.360	.081		4.432	.000
Social Media Engagement	.815	.027	.805	30.665	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Westernization

The B Unstandardized Coefficient shows a strong effect of social media engagement on consumers' westernization. For every 1-point increase in social media engagement, consumers' westernization is predicted to increase by 0.815 points (holding all other variables constant). Furthermore, the R Square test of model fit indicated that approximately 65% of the variance in consumers' westernization can be explained and predicted by social media engagement. Therefore, H5 is accepted.

When comparing the individual effect of social media involvement on the study's dependent variables, as indicated by the standardized Beta coefficients in the above-mentioned regression analysis tables, we conclude that the most substantial effect is negatively associated with consumer satisfaction with one's own body image (-0.893). Respectively, the positive effect is demonstrated on consumers' westernization (0.805), impulsive buying online

(0.774), attention to social comparison online (0.77), and finally on consumers' materialism (0.730).

To investigate the interrelationships among dependent variables in light of social media involvement, partial correlations and bivariate Pearson correlations are used to compare results before and after controlling for social media involvement's effect on the remaining variables. Table 8 presents the partial correlations of the study's dependent variables (controlling for social media engagement), and Table 9 presents the bivariate Pearson correlations. When comparing the results of Partial versus Pearson correlation analyses of the interrelationships among all dependent variables, it is evident that consumers' social media involvement amplifies these interrelationships, whether positively or negatively.

Table 8: Partial correlation of the dependent variables of the study.

Controlling for the effect of Social media engagement		Impulsive Buying Online	Social Comparison Online	Satisfaction with Body Image	Materialism	Westernization
Impulsive Buying Online	Correlation	1.000	.928	-.869	.430	.306
	Sig (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000	.000	.000
	df	0	511	511	511	511
Social Comparison Online	Correlation	.928	1.000	-.861	.431	.321
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000	.000	.000
	df	511	0	511	511	511
Satisfaction with Body Image	Correlation	-.869	-.861	1.000	-.448	-.333
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.	.000	.000
	df	511	511	0	511	511
Materialism	Correlation	.430	.431	-.448	1.000	.259
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.	.000
	df	511	511	511	0	511
Westernization	Correlation	.306	.321	-.333	.259	1.000
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.
	df	511	511	511	511	0

8. Conclusion

The study's findings indicated that the majority of Kuwaiti respondents had a moderate level of social media involvement. In addition, data analysis revealed a strong effect of social media involvement on Kuwaiti consumers' lifestyle, including a positive effect on their online impulsive buying and attention to social comparison online, and an adverse effect on their satisfaction with their own body image. Results also indicated a significant positive effect of social media involvement on consumers' materialism and westernization in Kuwait. These findings are consistent with previous literature and with similar research conducted across different cultures. However, the findings of the current research shed light on the strength and significance of social media's impact on consumers' lifestyles, materialism, and westernization within the Arabian Gulf culture, particularly in Kuwait. In addition, the findings showed that social media involvement amplifies the interrelationships among the study's dependent variables, thereby enhancing the significance, magnitude, and importance of this effect on consumers' social and financial decisions.

Table 9: Bivariate Pearson correlation of the dependent variables of the study.

		Impulsive Buying Online	Social Comparison Online	Satisfaction with Body Image	Materialism	Westernization
Impulsive Buying Online	Correlation	1	.971	-.939	.752	.738
	Sig (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	514	514	514	514	514
Social Comparison Online	Correlation	.971	1	-.935	.750	.741
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	514	514	514	514	514
Satisfaction with Body Image	Correlation	-.939	-.935	1	-.790	-.808
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	514	514	514	514	514
Materialism	Correlation	.752	.750	-.790	1	.693
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	514	514	514	514	514
Westernization	Correlation	.738	.741	-.808	.693	1
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	514	514	514	514	514

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